

Modified Bose-Einstein or Fermi-Dirac Distributions Due to Momentum Wavefunction?

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In previous notes, we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions are derivable from elastic scattering balance arguments. For example, for FD or BE cases, one may use $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $f(e_1)[1 \mp f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1 \mp f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1 \mp f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1 \mp f(e_2)]$ ((1a)). Taking \ln of the latter and linking to the former yields the distributions. For the BE case, there is an enhancement (1) of $f(e_i)+1$ for a boson to scatter into a state e_i occupied by $f(e_i)$ bosons. This follows from assuming that n bosons (a,b,c, etc) scatter into states (1,2,3...) with such similar momenta (magnitude and direction) that they may be treated as the same state. Thus, there is a lack of resolution in momentum phase space and also overcounting.

In this note, we try to consider the interplay between quantum statistical behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ waves and the statistical approach of scattering. Scattering assumes a specific energy and momentum, but single particle wavefunctions, especially those inside a "box" have a momentum distribution with an average momentum and distributions (e.g. $\sin(px)$). As a result, the single particle wavefunction only represents the average momentum for a portion of the time (hopefully a large portion). Nevertheless, we ask whether one may obtain a more accurate result by considering a factor $A(e_i)$ related to the variance of the momentum wavefunction and replacing $f(e_i)$ with $W(e_i)f(e_i)$. In a collision, both momentum and energy come into play. Thus, different wavefunctions (due to different potentials) have different momentum distributions which seem to affect the scattering picture used in (1), in particular the resolution of the scattered states. For example, nucleons in a hot nucleus may be approximated as almost being in a "box" (i.e. a Fermi gas).

In this note, we find that the overall form of the FD or BE distribution may remain the same, but are multiplied by a factor $1/A(e_i)$ which seems to play the role of modifying the phase space cell size.

Statistical and Quantum Mechanics

Both quantum and statistical mechanics are statistical theories, as mentioned in previous notes, but of a different nature. Quantum mechanics seems to be largely related to the establishment of a single particle resonance of $\exp(ipx)$ objects in a potential. This potential, however, may be due to other quantum particles in a statistical (thermal) equilibrium as in a hot nucleus. Thus, statistical and quantum mechanics are intertwined (as in the temperature dependent Hartree-Fock approach). The quantum particles, which are in a resonance state which is described by discrete energy levels, however, may scatter with other quantum particles which are part of a thermal equilibrium. Thus, one often sees the Fermi-Dirac distribution $f(e_i) = 1 / [1 + \exp((e_i - \mu)/T)]$ used for fermions, where e_i is the single particle energy level. e_i may in fact be a function of T as the potential may be created by other quantum particles in thermal equilibrium. Thus, there seem to be two processes occurring in a hot system of fermions or

bosons. The fermions or bosons try to form a resonance by interacting with a potential i.e. an instantaneous representation of an $\exp(ipx)$ boson or fermion may interact with the $V(x)$ expanded in a Fourier series to create a resonance marked by e_i which is related to $\exp(i e_i t)$ ($\hbar=1$). Various resonances (marked by i) may be created, each with energy e_i even in a hot quantum “approximated gas” such as a hot nucleus.

A quantum resonance, however, is metastable i.e. a particle may remain in it for a long time. The collisions between particles, which one the one hand represent a particle interacting with $V(x,T)$, may also knock a particle from one e_i to another, e_j . This is a second statistical process occurring in a hot gas. The question is how many particles, on average, occupy $f(e_i)$ or for what percentage of time is e_i occupied (again $f(e_i)$) for a set of fermions? Similar arguments should apply to bosons. This seems to be related to scattering among different $f(e_i)$.

Thus, two events appear to be occurring. First, interactions between various fermions (or bosons) create a potential $V(x,T)$. A quantum object, represented by $\exp(ipx)$ at an instant, with p changing, interacts with $V(k,T)\exp(ikx)$ Fourier components of the potential to try to create a resonance in time. This resonance, however, may be upset by a collision which tries to knock a particular $\exp(ipx)$ into a higher e_j level. For thermal equilibrium, one wishes $f(e_i, T)$ to be independent of time. It seems it is the most probable momentum p components of the wavefunction of e_i which are involved in collisions which knock an e_i into an e_j , if one wishes to consider elastic collisions.

Statistical Collisions Knocking e_i into e_j

Quantum resonances lead to single particle eigenstates e_i which have kinetic energy and potential energy, or in some cases, only kinetic (either nonrelativistic or relativistic). Statistical collisions which knock a quantum particle in an instantaneous state $\exp(ipx)$ from one e_i to another seem to be elastic and should be associated with a specific momentum, for one to consider physical scattering and use $dV d^3p / h^3$. Otherwise, one treats the Bose-Einstein or Fermi-Dirac distributions in a discrete manner, summing over e_i . For a Fermi gas, one uses $dV d^3p / h^3$, but even eigenstates $C\sin(px)$ $x=0$ to $x=L$ with $p=3.14n/L$ have a momentum Fourier transform which involves all momentum waves $\exp(ikx)$. There is a peak for $k=p$, where p is the average momentum. For different kinds of “boxes”, this momentum distribution may be a little different, although a strong peak around a certain p should be common to all. We argue in this note that the variance of this peak may have some significance for the derivation of the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein distributions.

In order to see this, consider calculating the Bose-Einstein distribution from a scattering point of view.

As argued in the introduction, the BE distribution follows from: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $f(e_1)[1+f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1+f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1+f(e_2)]$ by taking \ln of the latter and linking to the former. This suggests an enhancement factor of $[1+f(e_i)]$ for scattering into a state e_i which has $f(e_i)$ bosons. How is this enhancement factor derived? In (1), it is argued that n bosons (a,b,c,\dots) scatter into states $(1,2,3,\dots)$. Thus, one writes an amplitude squared as:

$$| a_1 b_2 \dots + a_2 b_1 \dots + \text{etc} |^2 \quad ((2))$$

There are $n!$ arrangements and if one assumes, as in (1), that all final states (1,2,3...) are the same, then one obtains the factor $(n!)^2$. The final states (1,2,3,...), however, are not the same. They may have slightly different momentum magnitudes or directions, thus there is a loss of resolution in momentum phase space in quantum mechanics due to the uncertainty principle (or momentum distribution of the momentum wavefunction) and also overcounting of states. Finally, a $1/n!$ factor is obtained by arguing that the area $(\Delta S)^n$ overcounts by $n!$.

Treating all final states (1,2,3...) as identical and using a factor of n is an approximation. Is it possible to obtain a more accurate approximation? It seems one uses the idea of a lack of resolution in momentum space. For the thermal equilibrium of bosons in a box, there is already a lack of momentum resolution due to the wavefunction itself i.e. the momentum Fourier transform. For example, $\sin(px)$ with p being average momentum, has a Fourier transform (given in the literature and related to the Fourier transform of step functions at the walls). This momentum wavefunction peaks at p , the average momentum, but has a distribution with a variance. If instead, the distribution were very sharp, one would argue against dropping resolution in momentum space and use the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

It seems, however, that there is another consequence of a lack of momentum resolution as governed by the single particle momentum wavefunction. We argue that even though a particle has an average momentum, part of the time its momentum is not near this average value. The sharper the momentum wavefunction peak, the closer to the average momentum. It seems different momentum wavefunction distributions should lead to different scattering i.e. one can only consider the particle to be scattering with average momentum p for $A(e_i)$ of the time.

Thus, we suggest a factor $0 < A(e_i) < 1$ linked to the variance of the momentum quantum single particle wavefunction. We do not give a specific recipe for this factor, so one may try different scenarios to see if there is any agreement with experimental data. For example, one might let $A(e_i)$ be the fraction of the momentum wave function squared that is within x percent of p average. We apply this approach to box like potentials for which the quantum particles have almost a $\sin(px)$ wavefunction.

As an approximation, we replace $f(e_i)$ with $A(e_i)f(e_i)$ everywhere in ((1a)) to obtain:

$$A(e_i)f(e_i) / [1+f(e_i)A(e_i)] = \exp[-(e_i-u)/T] \text{ or } f(e_i) = 1/A(e_i) [1/(\exp((e_i-u)/T)-1)] \quad ((3))$$

Thus, $1/A(e_i)$ seems to play the role of modifying the phase space cell size. We argue that even for collisions, $\sin(px)$ only represents a particle with a momentum close to p , the average momentum, part of the time.

Consider the Fermi-Dirac case. Imagine a state e_i represents an average momentum p_i , but with a variance. Thus, perhaps only $A(e_i) f(e_i)$, where $A(e_i)$ is a fraction related to the variance, corresponds to p_i (or close to it). Thus, if one considers a reaction represented by e_i and p_i then:

$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1-f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)]$ may be replaced with:

$A(e_i)f(e_i)$ because only this fraction of $A(e_i) f(e_i)$ really represents e_i, p_i . Later, one uses $dV d^3p / h^3$ to “sum” over e_i states. The FD result is: $f(e_i) = 1/A(e_i) [1/(1+\exp((e_i-u)/T))]$

Arbitrariness of Modification Factor

In the above, one may note there is an arbitrariness to the modification factor $A(e_i)$ of $f(e_i)$. This is true, but the argument we try to make is that different box potential wavefunctions may give rise to slightly different Bose-Einstein or Fermi-Dirac distributions and that one may be able to see this experimentally. In other words, we try to add a correction to the idea that one may simply associate an average momentum p_i (vector) with a box wavefunction state e_i . One may for example, obtain the square of the momentum wavefunction and calculate what fraction lies with plus/minus x percent of the average momentum and use this as $A(e_i)$. It seems, however, one may wish to have sharply peaked momentum wavefunction distributions in order to take this modified scattering approach seriously. In such a case, $A(e_i)$ may be fairly close to 1.

Relationship to Phase Space Cell Size

In (2), it is argued that expanding the maximization of factorial arrangement equations, subject to constraints $\sum_i f(e_i) = N$ and $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{total}$, for various distributions (in particular the Maxwell-Boltzmann) leads to an enhancement of the distribution. This approach is not related to quantum single particle wavefunctions (even if it were to be applied to factorial arrangements which lead to the FD or BE distributions) i.e.

FD $g(e_i)! / [n(e_i)! (g(e_i) - n(e_i))!]$ where $g(e_i)$ is the degeneracy and $n(e_i)$ = the number of particles with $n(e_i)$

BE $[g(e_i) - 1 + n(e_i)]! / [(n(e_i))! (g(e_i) - 1)!]$

In (2), the enhancement is said to be related to a change in the phase space cell size.

Here we try to argue that $1/A(e_i)$, which follows from the momentum wavefunction, may also represent a modification of the momentum phase space cell. Given that $A(e_i) < 1$, phase space is multiplied by a number greater than 1. For normalization relationships:

Integral $dV d^3p / h^3 \cdot 1/A(e_i)$ (FD or BE distribution) = $\langle N \rangle$ and

Integral $dV d^3p / h^3 \cdot e_i/A(e_i)$ (FD or BE distribution) = E_{total}

where $1/A(e_i) > 1$. This should affect the value of the chemical potential and T for an FD or BE distribution with $\langle N \rangle$ particles and E_{total} .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that a single particle wavefunction for box type scenarios which represent an average momentum p (e.g. $\sin(px)$), contain many momentum components in the momentum wavefunction (Fourier transform of the wavefunction). The momentum distribution is hopefully peaked, but has a variance. We argue that when establishing the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein distributions using scattering arguments ((1a)), one should replace $f(e_i)$ with $A(e_i)f(e_i)$, where $A(e_i)$ is a modification factor “obtained” from the momentum wavefunction distribution squared. $A(e_i)$ indicates that only a portion of $f(e_i)$, namely $A(e_i)f(e_i)$, carry a value close to the average p_i . It is this only this portion which may be meaningfully used in an elastic scattering reaction, we argue. The FD and BE distributions remain unchanged, but are multiplied by $1/A(e_i)$ which appears as modification to the momentum portion of the phase space cell size. There is some arbitrariness in choosing $A(e_i)$, but perhaps it may be fit from experiment. More importantly, different box type potentials may give rise to different $A(e_i)$ which may be noticeable. For example, nucleons in a hot nucleus may be approximated as creating a Fermi gas.

References

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